

Artificial Intelligence Usage and Ethics in the Choice Theory

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is surprisingly hard to define the term in the modern world. Although there are hopes harbored in development in progress based on the AI, there are also ethical doubts and questions related to this matter. The main goal of this paper is to discuss the main definitions and elaborate on one approach for future qualitative research. This paper presents a review of definitions in a view of ethics and choice theory. Definitions are presented early ideas to the big data era to set a decision-making problem. The presented research is important because most of the industry sectors depend on technology and computers in particular.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Artificial Neural Networks, Decision-making Problem

Introduction

The topic of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to most people sounds like the current state of the art of the computer sciences (Yazdani and Kwaśnicka, 2016) or like a futuristic term taken from Isaac Asimov's novels (Asimov, 2004). We are living in times when AI became one of the disruptive and trendy terms and it almost seems like marketers just add it to the product as a feature (Stępień, 2019), which makes a toothbrush being advertised like a lightsaber or trashcan like R2D2 (Lucas, 1976). From the beginning of the human race, dexterity and intellect have been its domain, which enabled it to settle in almost every environment in every single place of the world (Niemczyk et al., 2018). To call a computer code Artificial Intelligence, which means that it can mimic the functionality of the brain, to some of the population is somehow offensive and it undermines the achievements of our ancestors (Sulich, Zema, et al., 2020). This term has been invented to rise this type of feeling. Some people, when they hear it automatically get offensive and contrary to that, some people see AI as a promise of a better future (Krzos and Olek, 2019). Either way, everyone will admit that this mixed usage of biological and IT terms rises a discussion at many levels. At the most recent, looking at the people's attitude to AI it seems like the majority of humanity decided, that if they cannot stop it, they may also "enjoy the ride" and get accustomed to self-driving vehicles (Gontarz and Sulich, 2019), custom phone applications, but also chatbots and surveillance of public activities.

From the Early Ideas to the Big Data Era

The scientific environment is not consistent when it comes to the definition of AI (Duan et al., 2019; Górski and Parkitna, 2008). It is widely accepted that AI refers to the ability of the machine to learn to fulfill human-like tasks based on the input data (Duan et al., 2019). The term *artificial* suggests that the model is based on the scientific approach and as an outcome, we get synthetic creation. There are several approaches to the definition of Artificial Intelligence. One of them is to put this term into the field of science of building computer-based *artifacts* or *items* mimicking various human tasks (Niemczyk et al., 2018). This approach gives a wide range of philosophical discussions about the nature of intelligence and how it is created (Sulich and Zema, 2017). It also puts under the question if the machine is making any decision because it is based on the previously-made decisions by the creator of the system (Ćwik et al., 2017). Also, automated tasks cannot be called intelligence, because there is no decision making involved. The machine is simply following given instructions and it is limited to possible situations that may occur at the time. This raises a question on how to "teach" a machine to make decisions as humans do (Niemczyk et al., 2018). Similarly, to humans, computers can learn to make decisions based on the observation of the decision-making process. The artificial intelligence algorithm always follows the similar steps which mimic the process of learning: Identification of phenomena, construction of artificial system designated to solve recognized phenomena, operation of the system in a given environment, data gathering, assessment of the outcome under given boundary conditions. This process of learning also takes under consideration failures in solution to drive them back to the database (Nürk, 2019; Steels, 1993). If we, therefore, consider AI as a field of science aimed at imitating people, we cannot omit the topic of human reasoning. The problem is that each person follows his or her reasoning while making a decision. From this point of view, AI becomes cognitive science more than a study of computers. These different views led scientists to further research on how human beings can live alongside AI and how to minimize the negative impact of technology.

Fig 1. AI papers published in SSIS/IJMJ by year. Source: (Duan et al., 2019).

Reportedly, the AI systems are heading business to the new tracks and AI-enabled systems usage in corporations is expanding rapidly. The improvement is seen in the organization's ability to make data-driven predictions and has significantly reduced the cost of model preparations. According to some surveys AI is listed as the most strategic technology, which will reinvent business models and ecosystems, enhance decision making and reinvent the customer experience. The potential payoff of investment is predicted to happen in 2025 since 59% of organizations are still on the phase of information gathering and building their AI models, while the remainder is at the early stages of adaptation (Panetta, 2017). Although AI comes with great promises, early adopters are being cautious and pilot programs always give valuable lessons to future utilities. There is still a certain dose of dissatisfaction among academics with the lack of theoretical fundamentals and formulations. The aforementioned "AI springs" and "AI winters" among the history of the method has led to ignorance of research findings from years 1970 to 2000 and reinvention of concepts known from over four decades.

Decision-making Problem

The decision-making problem occurs when an individual or a group of people develop an idea of the desired state. This state often differs from the current situation, which requires certain actions to be undertaken. The aim is to prepare this set of activities, which will change the current situation to the target state in the short or long term. This difference between current and aimed state does not represent a decision-making problem, it appears when the goal can be reached by many means and ways. The decision-maker is then required to examine a set of possibilities to take the right course of action. The frequent negligence is not to investigate multiple possibilities but go straight away to action after inventing the first solution, whereas in almost all situations there is more than one option. A systemic approach is then highly advised and it will prevent the rush of being satisfied with the first idea. It is proven that a systemic approach provides better quality solutions in most cases. The decision-making problem can be then characterized by two main factors (Grünig and Kühn, 2005):

- A difference between the current state and the target state.
- At least two options for action to achieve the target.

The decision-making problem was widely recognized by both academics and practitioners, who proposed techniques including methods, models, algorithms and software tools (Zhang et al., 2015). The classification of different decision-making methodologies was undertaken by Zachary in his publication from 1986 (Zachary, 1986). According to his insight, we may distinguish the following decision-making techniques:

- Process models
- Choice models
- Information control
- Analysis and reasoning techniques
- Representation aids
- Human judgment amplifying/refining techniques

Most of these techniques include computational models with different emphasis on specificity like data mining, probabilistic modeling, data warehouse, goal programming, evidential reasoning, case-based reasoning, graphic user interface, heuristic judgments. The systemic solution of the decision-making problem may also include the integration of two or more techniques. AI finds its roots in heuristic methods and therefore in Zachary's taxonomy, it can be classified as Human judgment amplifying/refining technique (Zachary, 1986). Although Zachary's opinion on heuristic methods is not overly flattering, the change that they have faced over the years made them fairly popular and appreciated.

The decision is undertaken to reach the desired state, which differs from the current one. Although this problem may be approached from many perspectives: purely intuitively, without closer investigation of the problem, through described procedures taken from own or others experience, by taking a solution based on the expert knowledge or even choosing at random. All of these methods can be applied in different scenarios, but when it comes to the consistency of the outcome only systemic approaches give satisfying and predictable results (Sulich, Zema, et al., 2020). The rationality in decision making rises a question on layers of philosophy, logic and probabilistic theories. We, as people, tend to make rash decisions and act under the influence of the environment we are living in (Sulich, Rutkowska, et al., 2020).

Artificial Neural Networks

Work on Artificial Neural Networks has been motivated by the development of neuroscience. The discovery of the complexity of human brain functionality has triggered the change in conventional computer architecture. The conventional PC is based on linear operations, whereas the brain makes complex, nonlinear, and parallel computations every second. The main cell which is responsible for making this operation is a neuron and it is more efficient than any modern processor. When we consider basic everyday tasks like senses perception, the information processing takes brain approximately 100-200 ms, which is even beyond the capabilities of supercomputers. The other example may be taken from less cognitively evolved creatures than humans. Bats are using echolocation for perceiving the velocity and size of the object when flying in the dark. These complex computations are way more accurate than any of the available echo sonars, even though the bat's brain is a size of a plum (Haykin, 1994). In both cases, humans, as well as bats, were given this astonishing gift at birth. It does not grow that much in terms of the volume in the lifetime, but it builds up its structure and gains abilities through the experience it is exposed to. In the beginning, in the human body for the first two years of life, the brain is very flexible and has a high ability to the adaptation to the surrounding environment. This elasticity in adaptation is then crucial for the functioning neurons in the brain as information processors and so it is essential for the functioning of artificial neural networks. In general, neural networks are machines designed to mimic the cognitive process of a brain to solve a given task. The neural network is usually a computer system, which is designed to perform computations with the ability of self-adaptation through learning. This type of task with high intensity of interaction requires a special computer architecture with a lot of processing units called "neurons". Therefore we may quote the following definition of the neural network: A neural network is a massively parallel distributed processor made up of simple processing units that has a natural propensity for storing experiential knowledge and making it available for use (Haykin, 1994). The resemblance to the human brain has two layers:

- The learning process is based on acquiring experience from the environment;
- The main storage space of knowledge are neurons and synaptic weights between them.

The learning process modulates formulations between the neurons to adapt the model to solve the given task. This approach is already well established in theory and has enriched some successful applications in many diverse fields (Bernard and Samuel, 1985; Haykin, 1994). The neural network is also able to rebuild its topology by creating new synaptic connections, which is similar to the human brain in which neurons can die and create new connections as well. The main quality in terms of the utility of neural networks is the capability to adapt. The structure of synaptic connections can restructure and build new relations, which allows better adjustment to the surrounding environment. Minor changes in the environment can be easily incorporated into a neural network since the learning process is flexible and can be performed in real-time, which is especially valuable with nonstationary boundary conditions. Moreover, neural networks can transmit information from the cause to the effect (Marwala, 2015). The structure of the neural network determines the learning algorithm incorporated in it. Deciding on which system will be better in solving a given problem

than others, we need to consider aspects like computational limitations or calculation optimization. We may then consider the classification of artificial neural networks according to their architecture:

1. Single-Layer Feedforward Networks

Neural networks can be organized in the form of layers. In the simplest architecture of the system, the inputs layer of source nodes is projecting directly onto the output layer. Described mapping is only one-sided. This type of neural network has been presented in Fig. 2.1, where we have four nodes on both sides: input and output. The described network is called a single-layer network because there is only one layer of output computation neurons. We do not count the input layer of source nodes, because no calculation is performed there.

Fig 2. Feedforward network with a single layer of neurons. Source: (Haykin, 1994).

2. Multilayer Feedforward Networks

The other type of architecture of the feedforward neural network is extended to have hidden layers of computational neurons. They are called "hidden" nodes because they are not exposed to any of the sides of the model: input nor output. The role that they play in the model is to modulate data between input and output to provide a better solution. By adding hidden layers to neural networks, the performance of the system is enhanced. In this type of architecture, the input layer sends a signal to the computation nodes in the second layer, then the second layer sends a signal to the third layer and the chain of information continues through all hidden neurons to the output layer. In the standard setup, the signal travels through all the layers respectively, without omitting any calculation nodes. The overall data transfer in a multilayer feedforward neural network from the input to output has been shown in Fig. 2.2. To shortly describe the illustrated neural network, we can use markup 10-4-2, which means that there are 10 source nodes, 4 nodes in the hidden layer and 2 output nodes.

Fig 3. Fully connected feedforward network with one hidden layer and one output layer, Source: (Haykin, 1994).

3. Recurrent Networks

A recurrent neural network in diversity to feedforward neural networks includes an additional at least one feedback loop. The recurrent neural network presented in Fig. 2.3 includes one layer of neurons with each neuron feeding its output signal back to the inputs of all the other neurons. We can also distinguish self-feedback loops, where each of the output nodes provides the information back to its input. Furthermore, see that network architecture from Fig. 2.3 do not include any hidden neurons. If that was a case, a feedback connection can originate from the hidden nodes as well as from the output nodes. At any stage of the feedback loop, the neural network can be exposed to additional input if needed. This type of architecture is the most commonly utilized, because of better overall performance and ability to provide sufficient solutions despite data scarcity. This system model is especially valuable if we have little knowledge about the data source.

The Hopfield network is a specific type of Recurrent Network in which every neuron has corresponding unit-time delays as shown in Fig. 2 and 3. The number of feedback loops is equal to the number of neurons. On every loop, the time-delayed element is input back to the network and feeds every other neuron in the model, so that self-feedback will not occur (Haykin, 1994). The Hopfield network is initiated by setting up the values of the units to the desired start pattern. The feedback loop continues until reaching the convergence, which is indicated when any value cannot be changed in the updating phase.

Fig 4. Recurrent network with no self-feedback loops and no hidden neurons, Source: (Haykin, 1994).

All of the presented neural network architectures may be used in the creation of the system, which will enhance the decision-making process. The most applicable one will be chosen according to the input data structure and the complexity of the solution we want to output. We also need to take into consideration available computational resources (Kwaśnicka et al., 1998).

Artificial Intelligence in Decision Making

The early idea of incorporation of Artificial Intelligence into decision making is the Expert System presented by Pomerol (1997). The basic functionality of this model is to process input information to diagnose the output. The strategy is to input the facts, which best describe the given situation and output the recommendation of action or assessment of the proposed solution. The best performance of the Expert System can be observed with controlling live parameters of the current process. According to input data, the system can assess the recent state and determine the action to undertake. The basic functionality of an expert system in comparison to the decision-making process has been shown in Fig. 5. Standard decision-making process consists of:

1. Diagnosis - a perception of a current state from the perspective of past and presence;
2. Choice of action - definition of multivalued function which describes the future states $\psi(S_i, A, E)$, where S_i is available current state, A is chosen action and E is an aftermath of action A ;
3. Look Ahead - the prediction of the future state according to A - action, and E - aftermath;
4. Preferences - maximization of the desired outcome.

Fig 5. The simplified decision process. Source: (Pomerol, 1997).

Expert Systems exclude user interference in decision making and that is why some academics describe them as being objective. On the other hand, there is a question of reliability on the system and that is why most system development is spent on verification of the inserted knowledge base. The interpretation of function ϕ is a set of rules supported by the system. This set can be a discrete function or fuzzy boundary conditions.

Knowledge-Based Improvement

The Knowledge-Based Improvement model introduced by Robinson et al. (2014) is presented. The main motivation behind the creation of this system was a curiosity about the decision-making process and eagerness to improve it using operating systems. Since sophisticated models are not always the best approach, the creator of KBI emphasizes that it is not meant to be complex. Instead, the main goal was enabling the prediction of an outcome of alternative decision-making strategies. Although it seems like a knowledge-based system has very limited capabilities, the author states that the real complexity of human decision making is impossible to model and so the involvement of decision-makers is vital in the process. In such a case, the main objective is to identify improvements to the decision-making strategies employed.

The KBI model has been shown in Fig 6 and it consists of five stages:

1. Understanding the decision-making process - At this stage, the decision-making process is being investigated. The recognition of decision-making strategy components like decision variables, decision options, decision attributes, and attribute levels is undertaken. We may take for instance the malfunctioning machine in an assembly line, as a case in which the person responsible for making the decision needs to decide: when to repair the machine and to whom he needs to hand-over this task. The decision variable may consider two options: immediate repair of the machine or waiting until it will stop working at the end of the shift. In the recognition phase, we need to take into account time, which will be needed for the repair and the type of failure, which will be taken as a main factor for the decision function formulation.

Fig 6. Knowledge-based improvement. Source: (Robinson et al., 2014)

To collect data from decision-makers we can make observations, but in many cases, it is very time consuming, because much time elapsed until the decision is reached. It is also difficult to note every significant decision-making factor solely based on observation, especially when most of them are changing in time. To solve this issue author of KBI proposes a Visual Interactive Simulation (VIS). In this case, the decision-maker is taking part in interactive simulation and being asked questions. The simulation ends with reaching a final decision by the user. The system then processes all collected data into decision variables $D_{i,j}$ and decision attribute A_i .

The decision-making process in KBI is represented with two-row vectors, where the first one represents a decision and the second one represents the attributes of the decision:

$$D_{i,j} = [d_1, d_2] \tag{1}$$

$$A_i = [a_1, a_2] \tag{2}$$

Where d - decision variables and a - decision attributes. The relation between both of this vector can be described with the function:

$$D_{i,j} = f(A_i) \tag{3}$$

Where $f(A_i)$ is a decision-making strategy. Since this function is unknown, we need to proceed with steps 1-3 to determine it with the help of AI techniques. In this case, a set of collected example decisions will be needed.

2. Data collection - After establishing, which factors determine the decision-making process we may start the data collection stage. In this step essentially the system creator needs to create a matrix of data relevant for decision making. In each example, the data source should include the value of each decision option and attribute level.

3. Determining the decision-making strategies - At this stage, all data collected by VIS are processed into decision variables $D_{i,j}$ and decision attributes A_i . These parameters are then used in the preparation of a decision-making strategy of individual decision-makers. We can create this model using the rule-based expert system or artificial neural networks. In most cases, an expert system is favored among the others because it can create decision trees, which represent the decision-making strategy and are more explanatory. In the decision, the tree system can assign priorities to each of the attributes according to the similarity to the data set with the correct decision. Since each decision tree represents one strategy there is a need for creating decision trees for each decision-maker.
4. Determining the consequences of the decision-making strategies - When all decision-making strategies are created for each decision-maker the next stage of KBI is to assess the results and choose the winning strategy. The simplest way to make such an assessment is to input expected results into Visual Interactive Simulation and compare it with a decision reached by the decisionmaker. Each time the decision is reached, decision attributes are passed to AI. Of course, the participation of best decision-makers is vital for the best performance of a system, since the winning strategy is chosen from those which participated in simulations. Any strategy reached this point can be improved and that is why we need to proceed to the last stage of KBI.
5. Seeking improvements - At this stage, only the best decision-making strategies are being considered in a search for optimization. There are two approaches to do that. We can create a discussion panel, which will aim to improve chosen strategies or we can make incremental changes by combining the best strategies. The alternative is to employ heuristic strategies with search algorithms. After optimizing the strategy, we need to verify it. We can do that by testing it in VIS.

There are clear benefits when using the KBI model. With the utility of VIS, we can collect data more efficiently. Moreover, we can control this input data at any stage of simulation. There is an ability to repeat the simulations with the same conditions, which is vital for verification purposes.

Conclusions

Most of the industry sectors depend on technology and computers in particular. In the USA we can hear that self-driving cars will lead to the unemployment of drivers. That may be the case in the future, but the labor market is constantly changing. In the past, there were thousands of people working on the connection of phone calls at the central office. Right now, it sounds almost ridiculous when we look at our smartphones. Fifty years ago, no-one would even think that people will be employed to write computer code and now millions of people are doing it and most of them are well off. The point here is that industry is constantly changing and we need to be aware that (Rudek and Heppner, 2020):

1. Even though some people may lose their job it is not happening overnight and there will be time to adjust to new conditions on the labor market;
2. Technology may take some of the jobs while creating new ones.

There is always a need to perceive emerging technology from different perspectives. Although some of the opinions sound very farfetched and alter reality it is good to exercise our trust. When we had our first sight on the internet most of the people didn't know how to approach it from a legal standpoint. The United States Government decided at the time to let this technology to freely develop. Thanks to this decision we have internet everywhere and it has enabled economics to move to completely new directions. The main obstacle which may stand on the way of evolution of Artificial Intelligence is over-legislation.

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